

Developing digital preservation, edition, and analysis of sources of medieval monophony and its theory

A Report from the *EarlyMuse* STSM in Würzburg, Germany

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Introduction

From July 21st to 25th, 2025, the Short-Term Scientific Mission “Developing digital preservation, edition, and analysis of sources of medieval monophony and its theory” of the COST Action *EarlyMuse* took place at the Institut für Musikforschung¹ at Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg (JMU), Germany, organized by Konstantin Voigt and Fabian C. Moss. Four participants had been selected by the *EarlyMuse* directory board for this mission: David Merlin (Deutsches Historisches Institut, Rom, IT), Alessandra Ignesti (Pavia, IT), Kelly Landerkin (Schola Cantorum Basiliensis, CH), and Michael Winter (Newcastle, UK). The program was enriched by members of the Würzburg musicology institute, namely Charles Atkinson, Martin Dippon, Tim Eipert, Jasmin Hartmann-Strauß, Andreas Pfisterer, as well as by Frank Puppe and Alexander Hartelt from the Institute for Computer Science at JMU who are important collaboration partners for the field of Optical Music Recognition (OMR), especially through their tool *OMMR4all*.² Elaine Stratton Hild (Boulder, Colorado) joined one of the sessions online and provided inspiring input. The meetings and work sessions took place at several locations: the musicology institute itself, but also working sites at the Würzburg Residence and the university’s new Zentrum für Philologie und Digitalität (ZPD).³

The program consisted of a rich and diverse set of talks and discussions as well as practical and writing sessions and, naturally, joint coffee breaks and dinners. This STSM was possible thanks to the generous support by the *EarlyMuse* COST Action and the Institut für Musikforschung in Würzburg.

¹ <http://musikwissenschaft.uni-wuerzburg.de/>

² <https://www.ommr4all.informatik.uni-wuerzburg.de/>

³ <https://www.uni-wuerzburg.de/zpd/>

From right to left: Charles Atkinson, David Merlin, Alessandra Ignesti, Michael Winter, Jasmin Hartmann-Strauß, Konstantin Voigt, Kelly Landerkin, and Fabian C. Moss.

Day 1: Monday, July 21, 2025

Corpus Monodicum: Project and state of work (Konstantin Voigt)

The long term edition project *Corpus monodicum - die einstimmige Musik des lateinischen Mittelalters* funded by the *Mainzer Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur* played a crucial role in transforming the Institut für Musikforschung into a place of digital scholarship in Medieval music. Running for 16 years - from 2010 to 2026 - the project is dedicated to closing the gap between the historic significance of monophonic music throughout the Middle Ages and the insufficient basis of editions for historiographical work could draw upon. The project founded by Andreas Haug provides editions of the genres of monophonic music newly created after the introduction of Roman chant into the Frankish realm after 754 - namely tropes, sequences, mass ordinary chants, latin songs and liturgical plays. Representing the products of a manuscript culture defined by the needs and practices of chant communities, CM is conceived as a source edition. For some genres it provides comprehensive editions of repertoires from certain geographical areas - such as proper-tropes from all French and German sources - for other genres, such as the vast repertoires of Mass Ordinary chants, the edition presents selected manuscripts in order to represent all items from at least one source. In 2010 *Corpus monodicum* started out as a conventional print edition. However, after having developed a prototype software for inputting the editions for the preparation of print - *Mono:Di*, developed by Thomas Weber and Elaine Stratton Hild based on the MEI Neumes module - the perspective of turning

Corpus monodicum into a fully digital edition emerged. Within a few years a substantial corpus of machine-readable editions had developed at a speed which allowed it to get far ahead of the schedule for printed volumes. Accordingly, Andreas Haug and the CM team decided to restructure the project with a focus on digital editions and development of digital infrastructures. In 2015 Frank Puppe joined Corpus monodicum as co-leader of the project and organized the development of the CM-Viewer (CM digital⁴), a substantial revision of the editing software for semantic encoding - established as Monodi+ by Felix Herrmann (Olyro) - and the development of the OMMR4all editor by Alexander Hartelt. Tim Eipert was put in charge of the data modelling for the project which then provided online-access to its edited materials. Currently the project is co-led by Frank Puppe and Konstantin Voigt and will provide the edition of almost 10.000 chants at its completion in December 2026. By now 5067 items are available in completed editions and 2000 more will be published with the next upload. Follow up projects are currently being developed and were also part of the discussion at this STSM.

While the STSM's program was planned around current research of the participants, the common line of work was centered around developing new fields of application of CM's digital tools for transcription and editing. Accordingly, learning to work with the Monodi+ editor — which will be available to the community in an open access format in 2026 - was the starting point of the first day.

Editing Monophony with Monodi+: Software demonstration (Tim Eipert)

Monodi+ employs the semiotically informed scholarly notation developed by Corpus Monodicum, which allows for an easily readable comparison of manuscript versions with different historical notations, while

retaining the relevant information on the historic notational syntax, such as neume-grouping, articulatory signs etc. Accordingly, Monodi+ allows for encoding various kinds of diastematic neumatic notations in a user-friendly and purpose-specific workflow. In this session, Tim Eipert introduced the program to the participants and explained its underlying hierarchical structure. This format allows various genres to be presented in ways appropriate to their specific forms. After a brief demonstration, the participants made their first attempts at data input in a

learning session using a strophic melody from Codex Calixtinus. Monodi+ proved itself to be a practical and efficient tool in the transcription of texts and pitches, with a clear workflow. Features such as the copy/paste function are advantageous to the transcription of repetitive structures such as sequences, hymns and strophic songs. Compatibility issues may exist with some browsers, and it is necessary to deactivate translation tools while inputting notes, in order to avoid superfluous translations. The annotation feature requires specific clarification, but its complexity allows for a variety of input options for use as a flexible tool for the critical apparatus.

⁴ <https://corpus-monodicum.de/>

Editing liturgical plays: concept and challenges (Elaine Stratton Hild and Kelly Landerkin)

In this session Elaine Stratton Hild and Kelly Landerkin discussed various aspects of editing liturgical plays for Corpus Monodicum. First addressing the question of the terminology and definition of the genre, they presented an overview of the sources and a general idea of the defining factor for a thematic identity of this genre: chants compiled into larger interactive structures based on performative indications in the manuscripts. Of the over 1000 surviving sources, CM has so far edited 20, consisting of 82 plays with 1174 individual chants

transcribed. The dialogues of Paris, B.n.F. fonds lat. 1139 served as a case study to discuss specific editorial challenges. Presenting some of the earliest dialogues among the known sources, the primary issues lie in the nature of the notation itself. The use of heightened neumes but without lines and clefs allows the pitches and intervals to be generally deducible, while a lack of scribal consistency regarding the amount of precision used in particular melodic segments leaves room for alternate solutions.

The presentation of the dialogues in Pa 1139 must ensure consistency within the framework of the editions of liturgical plays from all edited sources, while simultaneously offering editorial decisions that allow Pa 1139 as a whole to appear in a unified manner. This is a team effort, requiring coordination with various members of the Corpus Monodicum team. The necessity of this genre to codify two hierarchical levels in the edition - the play as well as its individual chant elements - presented the Monodi+ software with a challenge that led to a solution of layers that transparently conveys the reading of the source. The publication of these editions offers users an intuitive platform for interacting with these dialogues.

Day 2: Tuesday, July 22, 2025

Printed chant books and notation in Winterburger's Gradual (David Merlin)

The presentation began with an overview of the earliest printed liturgical sources (ca. 1457–1566). A brief panorama of the landscape of open-access databases on printed liturgical and musical-liturgical sources was offered. The figure of the print master Johannes Winterburger (fl. 1492–1519) was discussed, who led a printing shop in Vienna and produced eighteen liturgical volumes containing musical notation, for no fewer than four different bishoprics. Some of these editions were evidently intended for being used in more than one diocese, reflecting a pragmatic marketing strategy (particularly in relation to the bishoprics of Passau and Vienna). These issues are crucial for understanding the transmission and regional adaptation of liturgical repertoires (and its notation). Moreover, the presentation shed light on the internal diversity of

what has traditionally been referred to as ‘German Gothic notation’ (Stäblein-Szendrei 2001). Based on the analysis of specific neumes, it is possible to distinguish at least three distinct variants—referred to here as ‘dialects’ or ‘families’—which were distributed across different regions of the Holy Roman Empire. These variants reflect both German and Messine notational influences, providing valuable insight into the regionalisation of liturgical music notation. A focus of the presentation was Winterburger’s use of a particular notational sign—realised as a single printing type—which appears in at least four different musical contexts. This multiplicity of usage reveals a sophisticated level of typographical economy and adaptability.

Finally, a hand-out designed for practical, hands-on work with the digital tool OMMR4all, specifically applied to Winterburger’s Gradual, was distributed to the participants. This includes comparative neume tables drawn from both printed and manuscript sources, with a focus on Winterburger’s editions, enabling users to engage directly with the notation and explore its historical significance.

OMMR4all (Frank Puppe & Alexander Hartelt)

The digital tool OMMR4all (“Optical Medieval Music Recognition for everyone”) was developed at Würzburg University under the leadership of Frank Puppe in the context of the long-term academy edition project “Corpus Monodicum: Die einstimmige Musik des lateinischen Mittelalters” (Andreas Haug and Frank Puppe).⁵ Over the course of the project, the tool has been constantly refined, functionalities and features were added, so that it now provides a comprehensive workflow that starts with a digitized source of medieval monophonic notation – an image – and provides automated transcriptions of several musically relevant elements and dimensions: lines, layout (music versus text), notes, neumes, syllables, etc.

In these sessions, Puppe and Hartelt introduced the capabilities of OMMR4all, including a number of hands-on experiences. The participants had the opportunity to actively test the software and provide corrections as updated training data for the models to improve future output. It was agreed to continue the hands-on sessions on the fourth day. Quickly it became clear that OMMR4all is a valuable tool, especially for later sources. Moreover, it was very useful to have the Winterburg manuscript already prepared by Puppe and Hartelt as a working example to continue the focus on Merlin’s topic, while using it as the basis for getting to know the program. At the same time, it proved valuable for corpus building as it aids with transcription. Some editorial capacities lie outside of its scope and functionality, but those can be found in other tools, such as Monodi+. The participants reflected on possibilities to increase the adoption of such tools by a broader part of the community. Training sessions at conferences (e.g., MedRen) or via online

⁵ <https://corpus-monodicum.de/>

tutorials would increase value and open the tool to a network in a wider community. Musico Pratico: digitizing, translating, and analyzing Pontio's treatises (Fabian C. Moss)

Fabian Moss presented the upcoming project "Musico Pratico", a collaboration between the Würzburg institute and the Schola Cantorum in Basel, Switzerland, funded jointly by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG). The project focuses on the two 16th-century music theory treatises *Ragionamento di musica* (1588) and *Dialogo ove si tratta della theorica e prattica di musica* (1595) by Italian composer and theorist Pietro Pontio, and promises to create a digital translation as well as translations into German and English of the two texts. Moreover, the project will open up pedagogical perspectives and enable us to understand music from towards the end of the Renaissance through contemporary eyes. Important perspectives include questions of performance practice, composition/counterpoint and pedagogy. Topical areas such as dissonances little studied thus far, here is a chance for new insight.

Technically, the digital edition will be realized with collaborators at ZPD: Christian Reul and Torsten Roeder, who already used some of the material in digitization classes at JMU. The project will use the Würzburg tool OCR4all for optical layout and character recognition (see Figure below). Preliminary results show that this will deliver promising output, as the prints are highly legible and only few manual corrections will be needed. The project will moreover continue efforts for joint encoding of text and music with the most current versions of the TEI and MEI standards, respectively.

<p><i>farà ancho per segno dell'affettione, & offeruan-</i> farà ancho per segno dell'affettione, & offeruan- farà ancho per segno dell'affettione, & offeruan-</p> <p><i>Za mia verfo di loro; l'acettino dunque per quel</i> AZa mia verfo di loro; l'acettino dunque per quel Za mia verfo di loro; l'acettino dunque per quel</p> <p><i>maggior segno, che posso darle, & che da me può</i> maggior segno, che posso darle, & che da me può maggior segno, che posso darle, & che da me può</p>	<p><i>E con altro miglior modo, che</i> E con altro miglior modo, che E con altro miglior modo, che</p> <p><i>con l'attioni, si potesse dimoftrar</i> con l'attioni, si potesse dimoftrar con l'attioni, si potesse dimoftrar</p> <p><i>l'animo di chi ama, & offerua,</i> l'animo di chi ama, Fs& offerua, l'animo di chi ama, & offerua,</p>
<p>Top: Two random pages from Pontio's treatises, with layout recognition done by OCR4all. Bottom: Examples for OCR results with minor corrections done by student assistants.</p>	

9th-century music theory: Significance of the corpus and state of editions (Konstantin Voigt & Charles M. Atkinson)

The conception of “musica” as a discipline related to the practice of chant was one of the many new developments of the long 9th century. After the introduction of Roman chant in the Frankish realm in 754 the need for concepts which helped learning, understanding and transmitting the new repertoire must have been enormous. A first concept, documented since the end of the 8th century, was classification. The first tonaries started ordering chants not by liturgical criteria, but by melodic behavior, using a system of eight modes which had been taken over from Byzantium. During the course of the century, neumatic notations were developed from the accent signs of ancient grammar. Probably revising the paleofrankish model, Frankish, Breton, Lotharingian and Aquitanian notations allowed for elementarizing melodies by assigning one sign-element to each *sonus* of the chants notated. However, neither the classification of the tonaries nor the elementarization of neumes were concepts of pitch. This parameter was part of ancient harmonic theory, transmitted through Boethius and Martianus Capella and studied in glosses since the mid 9th century. This ancient *ars musica* was not perceived as a theory applicable to chant until the work of scholars such as Aurelian of Reome, Hucbald of Saint Amand, Regino of Prüm appeared towards the end of the 9th century. While different scholars followed different tracks, the common ground of these earliest cantus-treatises is the attempt to link the knowledge of ancient *ars musica* to the practice of chants and the concepts of practice-knowledge, namely modal classification and to a lesser extent notational elementarization. By redirecting the paradigm of *musica* from abstract and static mathematical proportions to the sounding melodies of chant, *musica* became a dynamic system of exchange between practice, pragmatic concepts and speculation. The treatises in which this fusion occurred are well known through critical print editions. These editions present comprehensive, philologically reconstructed texts, claiming it to be “originals”. The manuscripts serve as “Überlieferungsträger” - text witnesses - in these editions. However, in a manuscript culture, manuscripts carry more than a good or bad version of a text to be constituted. They reveal the individual circumstances for which a text was being copied and the interests that scribes and users had in the texts. In three case studies, Konstantin Voigt, Charles Atkinson and Jasmin Hartmann-Strauß showed why and how a digital edition of 9th century Latin music theory should bring the individuality and materiality of manuscripts into the focus of editorial work. This project -

currently in a preparatory stage funded by the Research fund of the faculty - has the potential to show the well known treatises in a different light, more oriented towards the historic reality of medieval text production and transmission.

Case study I: Regino of Prüm – *Epistola de harmonica institutione* (KV)

The *Epistola de harmonica institutione* by Regino of Prüm is a striking example, why manuscript transmission of Latin music theory matters. The two oldest manuscripts - Leipzig and Bruxelles - transmit radically different versions: While the Bruxelles-version makes a short introduction to Regino's own tonary, the Leipzig version is almost triple in length. This length results from the presence of materials compiled from Boethius, Martianus Capella and the Martianus-commentary by Remigius of Auxerre. The question if Regino wrote a short introduction, which was extended by a learned compilation in a monastic context, or if the long text stood at the beginning has been intensely debated. Even though the long version is by now considered likely to be the "original", the short version cannot be ruled out. Even if this was the case, the existence of a short version, created by dropping all the material identified as ancient texts or their commentaries, deserves a separate editorial representation, as it shows how the text had been used in a specific context, as prologue to Regino's tonary. In the course of its transmission history, the text was either extended by glosses, additions and further diagrams, or excerpted and sometimes reintegrated into larger contexts. Therefore a digital edition, making the texts available as historic realities within their manuscript contexts is required.

The planned digital edition should contain:

- a. editions of all manuscript versions of the *Epistola*, including the relevant contexts, such as the tonary or surrounding texts.
- b. a constituted text, distinguishing the layers of redaction, addition and shortening.
- c. a display of all the ancient and medieval sources texts, accessible in full, with the concordances highlighted, both in the source edition and in the constituted text.
- d. a link of all chant examples to the cantus database and an MEI-encoding of the neumed incipits.
- e. english translations of all the text versions edited.
- f. a dynamic link of the editions to the available manuscripts via IIF.

Case study II: *Alia musica* (CMA)

The *Alia musica* is an even more complex case of textual layering, as four different authors left their traces in the text as it is now transmitted. The digital edition will follow the same principles as the edition of Regino's *Epistola* - a) all manuscript versions, b) a constituted text, c) display of source texts text, d) encoded and crosslinked chant examples, e) english translation, f) manuscript reproductions. Moreover the textual layering will be presented dynamically in the digital edition. As the functional prototype already developed shows, the text can be displayed in its editorial arrangement, or by separated layers.

Currently the application of OCR for creating diplomatic transcriptions is being tested and the data-modelling is being completed. As a result, we expect the digital editions of the *Alia musica* and Regino to provide the infrastructure for a growing corpus of latin theory texts edited in their manuscript versions. However, as the textual history of the *Alia musica* also demands for a "strong" editor, evaluating

and presenting the different layers, the infrastructure is designed to serve both, manuscript versions and critically constituted texts.

§51	Est autem integra diatessaron consonantia inter utrumque modum: dum lichanos hypaton hypodorii sit proslambanomenos dorii.	β
§52	Siquidem ex duplo et triplo hanc consonantiam procreari Boetius ita dicit: ² Sint hujusmodi medietatis termini, quorum extremi sint dupli, et alii quorum extremi sint tripli, ita: 6. 8. 12 - 4. 6. 12. ³ Duodenarius igitur ad senarium duplus est, et in alia dispositione 12 ad 4 triplus est. ⁴ Horum si differentias colligamus, et ad se invicem comparemus, epitrita proportio, id est diatessaron symphonia colligitur, et reliqua.	β
§53	[130] Cum haec ita sint, certum est quod paranete diezeugmenon hypodorii, cui adscribuntur 6, sit meses dorii. ² Ad quam mesen dorii se pervenerit cantus secundi tropi, jam potius dicetur dorii quam hypodorii, ³ ut est in responsorio gradali Universi qui te expectant. ⁴ Quod per differentiam quae est 12 passim excurrit inter bis 12 et 12, ⁵ cujus versus habens in responsorium primordio intensum diapente, a 18 videlicet in 12, percurrit 9, qui sunt differentia a bis 9 in 9. ⁶ Responsorium quoque nocturnale quod est Circumdederunt me cum suo versu unum tonum ultra differentiam quam diximus constare inter 24 et 12 acuendo peragit.	δ
ITEM DE SECUNDO TONO NOVA CUJUSDAM EXPOSITIO		
§54	A quarta specie diapason, quae est in e, ubi finitur primus tropus, inchoatur [186] et secundus. ² Ibique finitur, ubi et inchoatur. ³ Concluditur autem ejus forma intra diapente, quod est ab m ad c. ⁴ Hujus autem tropi haec est forma NOEAGIS.	γ
§55	Habet hic tropus differentiam in nocturnis unam in e quae habet tria loca: diatessaron remissum in a, ut Laetentur caeli; sesquioctavum remissum in c: Igitur; se ut Juste et pie. ² Unde constat ut hic tropus unam habeat differentiam in nocturnis, et tria loca.	γ
§56	In diurnis hic tropus ipsam habet differentiam et ipsa loca: diatessaron remissum in a, ut Ecce advenit; tonum remissum in c: Sitientes; se, ut De necessitatibus.	γ
§57	[187] Hujus tropi in nocturnis sic currit versus: Gloria Patri et caetera. In diurnis autem sic currit versus: Gloria Patri et caetera.	γ
SEQUITUR TONORUM EXPOSITOR DE TERTIO TONO		
§58	[133] Tertius tonus duo a habet, unum propter mensuram autenti deuteri, et alterum propter plagam ejus, in cujus diapason suum semitonium explicat, et alterum semitonium in diapason secundi toni, propter triplam ut dictum est, et quadruplam propter quater 6 ad unum 6 de primo.	β

Prototype of the digital Alia Musica Edition, designed by Torsten Roeder and Charles M. Atkinson:
Displaying text with marked layers

The discussion addressed a number of features desirable in such an edition, in particular the combination of TEI and MEI for encoding the neumed chant examples, the necessity of making the ancient source texts transparent to the modes of excerpting applied by the compilers of the *Alia musica* and the usability of the english translations in dynamic synoptic relation to the latin texts.

§155	Omnis enim musicae consonantia aut ad unum 2 habet in duplici, aut 3 in triplici, aut 4 in quadruplici, aut 5 in sesquialtera, aut 7 in sesquitertia. ² Denique, ut supra dictum est, ex 5 tonis et semitonis octavum perficitur diapason, qui est primus tonus, ut 6 ad 12, ad quem omnis musicae consonantia refertur.	α
§156	[97] Quicumque enim numerus ad 12 partiri potest, ita ut ad ipsum duodenarium sive per 3 et 4, sive per 4 et 3 dividatur, musicus est, constans in supradictis proportionibus. ² Nam Pythagoras aptavit duplam in 6, sesquialteram in 8, sesquitertiam in 9 ad 12. ³ Unde ex quinque speciebus tonorum: simplicium, id est diapente, diatessaron, diapason; compositorum, ut diapason simul et diapente, ut tertius tonus et sextus, et diapason ac diatessaron in eodem quinto, et dupla diapason in octavo tono, una cum duplo et triplo (...)	α
§181	[178] ITEM EXPOSITIO EORUMDEM TONORUM. [85] Tonus primus NONANOEANE, qui graece dicitur autentos protos, id est auctoritas prima, A 12, C 6, B 8, D 9. ² 6 ad 12 18 sunt, qui sunt ter 6, quae proportio dupla diapason dicitur. ³ Item 8 ad 12 20 sunt, quae proportio sesquialtera dicitur ad 12, ideo quia 12 habet 8 in se et alteram ejus partem, id est 4, et facit diapente. ⁴ Item 9 ad 12 21 sunt, quae proportio sesquialtera dicitur ad 12, quia 12 habet 9 in se et ejus tertiam partem, id est 3, et facit diatessaron, id est ter 7 qui sunt 21. ⁵ Omnis igitur primus tonus aut ter 6 habet in dupla proportione diapason, ut est Rorate celi desuper, aut quater 5, id est 2 de 8 et 3 de 12 in sesquialtera proportione qui faciunt diapente, quod est 20, ut est et nubes pluant justum, aperiatur; aut ter 7, id est 3 de 9 ad 4 de 12 in sesquitertia proportione, qui faciunt diatessaron, ut est terra et germinet Salvatorem. ⁶ Item Introitum Gaudete in Domino semper, et Justus es Domine; similiter antiphonae Urbs	α

Prototype of the digital *Alia Musica* Edition, designed by Torsten Roeder and Charles M. Atkinson:
Displaying text-layer Alpha separately

Diagrams in 9th-century Boethius manuscripts (Jasmin Hartmann- Strauss)

Jasmin presented the findings of her research on the diagrams in the handwritten tradition of Boethius' treatise. Approximately 100 diagrams across a corpus of around 160 manuscripts exist; 12 of these diagrams are found in manuscripts dating from the 9th century, all of which originate from France. The outcomes of the research were concisely summarized in five theses.

Following the presentation, the discussion first addressed the notion of vacant spaces within manuscripts which can stimulate the creative potential of scribes and illuminators. The idea of establishing a controlled vocabulary for the encoding of complex graphical elements such as tables, diagrams, and drawings was explored. This would facilitate more systematic and consistent representation of visual data in digital formats. Technical questions were raised regarding the methods and best practices for encoding diagrams, particularly those that embody epistemic content. Encoding such diagrams could enable comparative

analyses across different manuscript traditions and transmission lines. Furthermore, this would enhance accessibility, particularly for individuals with visual impairments, thereby supporting broader inclusion. While the visual composition of the manuscript page can be meaningful in itself, it was suggested that incorporating a “map of the page” within the encoded transcription may not be necessary, provided that the manuscript is freely accessible in digital form. In such cases, it remains essential to include a direct link to the digitized source. A final remark concerned the relative merits of browser-based platforms compared to database-driven systems. Browser-based solutions were considered to offer greater graphical flexibility and potential for creative implementations.

Day 3: Wednesday, July 23, 2025

Project presentation (Andreas Pfisterer & Tim Eipert)

Andreas Pfisterer introduced his follow-up project to CM focused on Old Roman Mass. The project aims to transcribe the Proprium Missae corpus of this tradition from three relevant manuscripts, all produced between the eleventh and thirteenth centuries. A search tool is planned that enables the comparison of parallel melodies and the identification of common variants by creating synoptical tables. A machine-readable, but scientifically sub-optimal corpus of transcriptions is already available for Mass

melodies through the Chant Digger tool⁶, developed by Max Haas, which encompasses the Gregorian, Old Roman, and Milanese traditions and allows searching for pitches in context, also in transposition, which is currently not possible in CM. With this tool in mind, Tim Eipert has been developing the prototype of a tool to search for pitch or interval sequences in Old Roman and Gregorian chant that relies on the Volpiano font,⁷ a simple but effective method for transcribing chant into modern stemless notation.⁸ The use

of multiple separate tools relies on the awareness that interfaces combining highly specific tools are preferable to a single tool that integrates different functions, which might get very complex and lack usability. Additionally, the modular architecture makes it easier to transfer to other cases and thus interesting for a wider community. Bruno Stäblein Archive (Martin Dippon)

On Wednesday afternoon, Martin Dippon presented the history, structure and holdings of the Bruno Stäblein archive. This collection, including numerous copies of sources produced by Stäblein himself, now also contains microfilms and photographs of manuscripts of music-theoretical treatises along with the library of books and articles of the project Lexicon musicum Latinum. This tour made clear the inherent

⁶ <https://chantdiggerweb.app/>

⁷ <https://www.fawe.de/volpiano/>

⁸ <https://timeipert.github.io/arc-prototype>

value of physical microfilm collections even in the digital age, with several examples of irreplaceable worth due to the loss or damage of the original source, and whole libraries that have been made available on public platforms such as Gallica or e-codices. Securing and creating a safe environment for these microfilms, and finding funding for the laborious process of their digitalization are vital next steps to continued access to these resources.

Microfilms between media history and digital future

At the conclusion of the visit in the Microfilm Archive the question was formulated regarding how to keep the archive as an active place of research and scholarship and not “just” a museum of holdings. The idea (or even wish) was proposed to organise “study days” on rare (or even nowadays no longer existing) manuscripts of liturgical chant and musical theory which are preserved as microfilms in the Stäblein Archive at the Institut für Musikforschung of the University of Würzburg. Besides the possibility of monodisciplinary study days focussed on the aspect related to musicological research, interdisciplinary meetings with experts of other fields – as for example digitalisation, library science – are thinkable. Archives still serve as valuable spaces and as meeting points for the scholarly community at large.

Indexing and classifying *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, 12–15th c. (AI)

This session was devoted to Alessandra Ignesti's presentation of the *Benedicamus Domino* Inventory (BDI), which aims to provide scholars with a comprehensive reference tool for the diverse and hard-to-define corpus of textual elaborations of the versicle and response pair *Benedicamus Domino: Deo gratias*. BDI has been inspired and initially developed within the context of the European Research Council (ERC) project *BENEDICAMUS: Musical and Poetic Creativity for a Unique Moment in the Western Christian Liturgy, c.1000-1500*, led by Catherine A. Bradley. It receives technical support from the *Digital Analysis of Chant Transmission* partnership project, led by Jennifer Bain and funded by the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC).

Currently under construction, BDI is conceived as a segment of the legacy database CANTUS.⁹ As such, it will enter the densely populated environment of online medieval music databases networked together by using unique identifiers known as “Cantus IDs” provided by the chant catalogue Cantus Index.¹⁰ Because CANTUS (and thus BDI) uses identifiers based on genre, the designing phase of BDI has required careful consideration of issues of classification raised by the multi-purpose and itinerant nature of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes. The negotiation between the needs of the new organism (BDI) and the structure of the hosting environment (CANTUS and Cantus Index) has inspired the adoption of a new conceptual framework for the classification of Ordinary chant tropes (to which *Benedicamus Domino* tropes belong) that was globally beneficial. The presentation included the description of the interface with the new fields designed for BDI within CANTUS and concluded with the discussion of a few challenging examples. Valuable feedback has emerged from the discussion, which has concentrated on the clarity of categorization (“What do we call a thing?”) and the compromise between accuracy, flexibility, and practicality.

Day 4: Thursday, July 24, 2025

Hands-on editing: Revision of the automatized transcription (Alexander Hartelt & Frank Puppe)

With the success of our introduction to OMMRforAll, we continued our work with the tool, transcribing work from Sens46. This was a useful hands-on session to gain more familiarity with the tools and to work towards creating a meaningful output: teaching the tool to recognize the specificities of the manuscript (text and notation). As well as this, we discussed ways in which the tool might be improved, based on our user experience. We considered the optimal workflow in using the tools, what recommendations we might make to new users, and the interaction and interoperability between OMMR4All and Monodi+.

The group discussed possible next steps for OMMR4All and how we might be able to encourage the wider musicological community to consider adopting the tool. Drawing on models from similar successful projects, we concluded that a wider dissemination of the tool would benefit from the inclusion of short instructional videos on the project website in order to ease the learning curve for new users. We also decided that one of our EarlyMuse STSM deliverables might focus on a report of the success and potential

⁹ <https://cantusdatabase.org/>

¹⁰ <https://cantusindex.org/>

of the tools, considering the experience of editing and its potential for producing editions of manuscripts and building corpora.

Digital tools in the reconstruction of the Eton Choirbook (Michael Winter)

In this session, Michael Winter presented aspects of his doctoral research, which considers methods of polyphonic reconstruction with a specific focus on the music of the Eton Choirbook (Eton College, MS 178). The Eton Choirbook survives incomplete due to loss of leaves from the manuscript. Due to the nature of the choirbook format in which each voice is laid out individually across an opening, the loss of a folio from the manuscript renders multiple voice-parts missing from a work. While this presentation deviated from the thematic focus of the STSM, the underlying research questions were nevertheless broadly similar.

The presentation demonstrated the use of digital tools (in particular CRIMIntervals¹¹) to analyse this *Eton* reperotry. It also demonstrated pilot-studies in machine-informed approaches to the reconstruction of fragmentary polyphony. These approaches included using a digital glossary to aid a pattern finding approach, and a primitive exploration of using AI to automatically reconstruct a fragment in order to consider what future directions might be possible. The digital tools were at their most successful being used to assist the editor. In particular, the ability to search a corpus for melodic, harmonic, and contrapuntal patterns was useful for considering whether a reconstruction completed by a human was idiomatic, or identifying moments in the surviving music which appear to be stylistically inconsistent.

By contrast, the value of AI to reconstruct the music of the Eton Choirbook seems to be more limited. Firstly, there is not currently enough of the corpus that has been digitally encoded for use with digital tools. Secondly, there might not be enough music, at all, from this time-period in England to build a strong enough digital corpus for use with powerful computational tools. We are also left with the question of what is lost to the editor by ceding part of the decision-making process to artificial intelligence. Much of the value in reconstructing this music lies not only in the end result, but in the insights gained through the act of reconstruction itself. Just because we might be able to automate something, it does not mean we should.

Tools for digital corpus analysis (Fabian C. Moss)

In the final presentation of the STSM, Fabian Moss summarized a couple of common threads of the previous presentations and, rather than presenting other digital tools for the analysis of musical corpora, focused on “mental tools for digital corpus analysis”. Arguing for terminological precision, he proposed to distinguish between collections (merely sets of things assembled according to at least one common organizing principle), datasets (requiring machine-readability and homogeneity of data formats), and corpora (a combination of the former two).

Moving to the issue of tools, he emphasized that it is not the tools that should define the research questions, but rather the other way around: scholarly research questions necessitate specific tools (“If all you have is a hammer, everything looks like a nail”). Rather than building tools that grow ever more complex, adding functionalities that make it difficult to maintain them, he argued that what is needed are solid toolkits, collections of interoperable software tools each of which addresses a limited set of needs.

¹¹ <https://github.com/HCDigitalScholarship/intervals>

During the discussions it became also aware that an “agile” mindset is helpful where tools are developed iteratively. Another thread was the terminology around classification, a central concern of scholars working with digitized manuscripts of medieval melodies. Items in categories are defined by some notion of mutual similarity. The task for automated classification is thus to “teach the machine what is significantly different” (Andreas Pfisterer).

In his closing remarks, Fabian Moss pointed out that in digital music editions the traditional boundary between basic and applied research becomes more fuzzy and can be understood as a spectrum rather than as a dichotomy. Lastly, he mentioned work that utilizes formal models from species ecology to estimate the proportion of a collection that is still missing. According to one such model, merely 50-70% of the entire chant repertoire has been catalogued, which implies for databases like Cantus that just because something is large it is not necessarily complete (nor representative).

Time-Slot for free-working

On Thursday afternoon the participants began preparing the final report of the activities of the STSM COST Action week in Würzburg in a collaborative writing session. Decisions on structure and content created the foundation for the work that continued on the final day of the session. Additionally, time was allotted to autonomous work on the scholars’ individual projects, as well as to continued experimentation with the tools introduced in the course of the week.

Day 5: Friday, July 25, 2025

On the final day of the STSM, the participants continued writing this report, and developed a comprehensive concept for an article to be published in an academic journal. The article will focus on user experiences and desirables regarding mass transcriptions and editions of monophonic medieval music, using OMMR4all and Monodi+ as examples. The output of this STSM will serve the scholarly community to better understand the capabilities, benefits, and limitations of software tools for automated transcription and analysis, and provide grounds for critical reflection as well as build a bridge to getting started with such tools. It is planned to produce a number of short videos that address common questions and issues when using the tools to further help new users (scholars and students) to engage with them productively.

Conclusion

This short-term scientific mission (STSM), enabled by the European COST Action *EarlyMuse*, facilitated the scientific exchange between experts on medieval chant, digital humanists, and computer scientists. The array of topics, ranging from the local Corpus Monodicum project to the guests’ individual projects, provided rich experiences and ample examples for extensive discussions. It became more than clear that digital methods can be useful additions to the musicologist’s toolkit, but also that it is equally important to possess a deep understanding of the source material and its historical-cultural context, as automated systems like OMR only see what is on the page. This STSM has moreover exemplified the importance of scholarly exchange between different researchers working on similar topics, not only because they may have different views about particular sources, but also because the interaction in working with the same tools can produce novel insights in how to edit or analyze music notation from a remote past.